

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ:
ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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YOSHLAR TARBIYASIDA OILANING O'RNI
THE ROLE OF THE FAMILY IN YOUTH EDUCATION
РОЛЬ СЕМЬИ В ОБРАЗОВАНИИ МОЛОДЕЖИ

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Annotatsiya. Tarbiya insonni komilikka eltuvchi yo'l. Tarbiya insonni ikki dunyo saodatiga yetaklovchi omildir.

Tayanch iboralar: Tarbiya ,oilа, dunyo, intizom, oliy – janoblik huquq, adolat ibn sino fikrlari ,Sa'diy Sheroziy fikrlari, Alisher Navoiy.

Abstract. Education is the path that brings a person to perfection. Education is a factor that leads a person to the happiness of two worlds.

Key phrases: education, family, world, discipline, supreme right, justice Ibn Sina's thoughts, Saadi Shirazi's thoughts, Alisher Navoi.

Абстрактный. Образование – это путь, ведущий человека к совершенству. Образование – фактор, ведущий человека к счастью двух миров.

Ключевые фразы: образование, семья, мир, дисциплина, высшее право, справедливость Мысли Ибн Сины, мысли Саади Ширази, Алишер Навои.

KIRISH

Tarbiya. Tarbiyani o'rni qanchalik muhimdir. Tarbiyani oilada qanday o'rni bor.

Oila jamiyat tayanchi hisoblanadi. Oilada tarbiya o'rni beqiyos hisoblanadi.

Aslida farzandga qachondan tarbiya berish kerak bo'ladi.

-Bir inson hazrat Ibn Sino oldiga borib so'rabdi:

- Men farzandimga qachondan tarbiya bermog'im zarur.

- Ibn Sino so'rabdi: " Farzanding necha yoshda? "

- Farzandim 3 yoshda .

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- “ Sen farzand tarbiyasiga kech qolibsana chunki farzand tarbiyasi ona qornida 3 oylikidan beriladi- ,” deb javob beribdi.

Yoshlar tarbiyasida oilani o`rni muhimligini shu yerda ham ko`rish mumkin bo`ladi. Shu sababdan farzand tarbiyasiga e`tibor qaratsak farzandimiz kelajakda yetuk shaxs bo`lib yetishadi. Bola tarbiyasi uchun ota-ona javobgar shaxs hisoblanadi . Farzandga to`g`ri tarbiya bermasak , masala ota –ona o`zi telefon o`ynasa-yu farzandiga tur darsingni qil kitobingni o`qi desa, farzand unga quloq solmaydi. Agarda ota-ona oliy ma`limotli bo`lsa , farzandi unga quloq solib unga taqlid qiladi, chunki bola taqlidchan bo`ladi. Oilada bolani muammolarini ota-ona birgalikda zimmasiga olmog`i lozim. Uni tushunib unga to`g`ri tarbiya bermog`i lozim. Ta`lim tarbiya yoshlikdan bermog`i lozim , chunki Rasullolloh (SAV) aytganlar. Birortangiz o`z farzandingizga tartib intizomga o`rgatsangiz har kun sadaqa bergandan yaxshiroq deydilar.

Ba`zilar tarbiyani ta`limdan ta`limni tarbiyadan ajratib bo`lmaydi deyishadi shuning uchun bu ishni maktab shug`ullasin deydi , lekin bu fikr mutloq noto`g`ri chunki bu ishni asosiysini oilada bilmog`i lozim. Farzand tarbiyasida bola huquqlarini kamsitish uning ruhiyatini buzishga olib keladi. Hozirgi kunda barcha bolani huquqlari qonun bilan belgilab qo`yilgan. O`z farzandiga to`g`ri tarbiya bera olgan ota-onalar umrlarini oxirigacha rohat- farog`atda o`tkazadilar. Oilani asosiy tayanchi bo`lgan ota-ona hayotning barcha mashaqqatlaridan totib ko`rgan, o`zining bukilmash irodasi adolati parvarligi hayot sinovlariga bardoshligi bilan ajralib turuvchi buyuk shaxs sifatida gavdalanadi.

Oilada ota-ona qandayligi farzandni kelajakda qanday bo`lishini ko`rsatib turadi. Ota-ona qanday bo`lsa farzand ham shunday bo`ladi. Chunki bola taqlidchan bo`ladi. U ota-onasida ko`rganini takrorlaydi. Shuning uchun ham bekorga qush uyasida ko`rganini qiladi deb bekorga aytmagan dono xalqimiz. Murg`ak tassavurli bola ilk tarbiyani oiladan oladi. Bolani ilk tarbiyasining sabablari haqida atiqli o`zbek pedagogi Abdulla Avloniy o`zining “Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq” kitobida quyidagi ibratli o`gitlar aytgan edi . “Tarbiyani tug`ilgan kundan boshlamak vujudimizni quvvatlantirmak lozim”.

Ota-ona bolaning xulqida xatti- xarakatida teskari munosabatda bo`lishi yaxshi emas. Yoki bola nojo`ya harakat qilsa-yu , ona qoralasa ota maqtasa yoki aksincha bo`lsa , bu xunuk oqibatlariga olib keladi. Agarda bolaning qilgan ishiga ikki xil munosabatda bo`lsa ham ular o`zaro kelishib harakat qilmog`i lozim.

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Xalqimizning “ oilaning boshlanishi kuyov-kelinchakdan, tarbiyaning boshlanishi belanchakdan “ degan ibora bekorga aytilmagan chaqaloq ham hali gapirmasdan oldin o`rgana boshlaydi.

Ota - ona mehrini bolaga g`amxo`rligini har kim turlicha namoyon qiladi. Bazilar o`zlarining mehr-muhabbatini qattiq qo`llik talabchanlik bilan ko`rsatadi. Oilada doimo bir biriga hurmat, ishonch, qadr qimmat, to`g`ri so`zlik va adolatli bo`lishi kerak. Bolani shu uyda o`rni borligini his qilmog`i zarur.

XULOSA.

Oila bu - jamoa. Unda o`zaro hurmat muomala barcha qoidalarga amal qilishi shart. Kattalarga hurmat, kichiklarga izzat , bir biriga mehribonlik ayniqsa ayollarga hurmat izzatda bo`lish kabi qoidalar bo`lmog`i shart.

Har bir ota-ona farzandini yaxshi ko`radi. Hech qaysi ota-ona farzandini yomon bo`lsin demaydi. Uni baxti kamolini ko`rishni istaydi. Farzandini baxti kelajagi uchun qayg`urish ota –onaning muqaddas burchi hisoblanadi.

O`sib kelayotgan yoshlarga Alisher Navoiyning mana bu nasihati doimo yodda saqlamog`i muvofiq :

Boshni fido qilg`il ato boshig`a

Jismimni qil sadqa ano qoshig`a

Tun kuningga aylangin nurposh koshig`a

Birisin oy angla birisin quyosh

Oilada jamiyat kishisi tarbiyalanayotgan bo`lajak mehnat kishisi tarbiyalanayotgan ekan. Bu har bir ota –ona mas`uliyati hisoblanadi. Yangi avlod yoshligidanoq tarbiyalanmog`i zarur. Sa`diy Sheroziy aytgan:

Kinga yoshligidan berimas odob

Ulg`aygach bo`ladi baxtsiz, dili g`ash

Ho`l novda egilar qay xil eksang

Quruqni to`g`rilar faqat o`t-otash

Ayrim pedagoglar uyda bola ko`p bo`lsa uni tarbiyalash qiyin deb o`yladi .Bu haqiqatga zid. Bola tarbiyasi ota-ona burchi. Lekin tarbiya xususiy ish emas. Bolani tarbiyasiga mas`uliyat bilan yondashmog`imiz kerak. Zero kelajak avlodga befarq bo`lmaylik.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO`YXATI:

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